

A Study on Traffic Safety, Risk Perception, Necessity of Traffic Education for School Students and Respect in Traffic

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Abstract

The concept of education is the phenomenon of developing positive behaviors in people through various methods and materials. In terms of traffic safety, the behavior of vehicle users is determined by their experience and education. On the other hand, traffic education concerns not only road users, drivers, passengers, and pedestrians, but also children of educational age and their educators, official units responsible for traffic control, academics, engineers who design and build roads and infrastructures, politicians, and large segments of society. Therefore, a human-oriented and sustainable traffic education can be considered as the most effective tool to ensure traffic safety in an ideal sense (Turkey Working Group Report, 2018). School-level traffic safety education provides students with information on how to drive more safely on public roads and highways. It is compulsory for these educations to start from primary school level. Although traffic knowledge and experience must be presented within the trainings, it is imperative that the concept of "respect" comes to the fore for students and individuals to gain good traffic knowledge and practice. It should not be forgotten that the purpose of these trainings is to provide lifelong traffic knowledge and skills. The importance of learning these skills at school level is increasing as increased students go to school today. Those who do not drive use either bicycles or motorcycles. Therefore, these groups are "vulnerable road users" and need special protection. All such students need to be given specific training on their own safety on the road and the safety of other road users.

Keywords: *Traffic Safety, Traffic Education, Traffic Teaching, Respect in Traffic, Traffic Education in Schools*

1. Introduction

a. Traffic Safety and Traffic Accidents

i. Traffic Safety Concept

The Turkish Language Institution defines the concept of security as “the legal order in social life without interruption, the situation where people can live without fear, safety” (TDK). (“The Problem of Illegal Immigration in the Eastern Mediterranean and Measures Taken at the Regional Level”) Traffic areas or traffic areas are also living spaces where the security threat can be felt at individual, social and environmental dimensions, where people need to live without fear and feel safe. Therefore, behaviors and situations that threaten traffic safety in traffic areas should be managed with long-term plans and policies (Özkan et al., 2018).

According to the World Health Organization's 2015 Global Status Report on Road Safety (World Health Organization [WHO], 2015a), road traffic crashes claim more than 1.25 million lives each year and have a major impact on health and development. It is the leading cause of death among youth aged 15 to 29, costing governments about 3% of their Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The fact that road deaths have remained constant at 22-25 per 100,000 people in the last ten years, and when road safety is taken more seriously, compared with developed countries presents a much worse picture (Mansuri et al., 2015). It is obvious that students and individuals cannot be ideal drivers at the desired level without traffic education and even without being taught the concept of respect in traffic.

The concept of traffic safety has developed as a concept that aims to minimize the injuries, property and life losses that occur because of traffic accidents in residential and non-residential areas. In this context, the concept refers to the fulfillment of services such as education, inspection, and engineering in accordance with scientific criteria to ensure a healthy and safe transportation in a country. In other words, traffic safety; It is the scientific implementation of education, planning, inspection, regulation, infrastructure, health-first aid practices to avoid or minimize traffic accidents (Yigitel, 2019).

ii. Increase in Traffic Accidents

With the increase in traffic accidents and the increase in loss of property and life because of accidents, the concept of traffic safety has started to gain importance, and at the same time, the interest in traffic safety education has increased. The knowledge and skills that are tried to be created in individuals through traffic safety education and awareness-raising activities. and behaviours accidents and accidents results formed material spiritual losses will reduce. Therefore, traffic safety education, which is important for public safety and health, should be started from an early age (Şimşek et al., 2009). The issue of traffic safety is a multidimensional issue based on the interaction of human, law, vehicle, and road elements. In this context, it is possible to describe traffic accidents as preventable safety problems that negatively affect social security.

b. Traffic Safety Elements of

“It is possible to consider the factors affecting traffic safety separately as direct and indirect factors.”

c. Directly Affecting Traffic Safety Elements

i. Path

In terms of traffic, a road is a stretch of land, fields and bridges open to the public for traffic. Accordingly, pedestrian roads, field, forest, and mountain roads are also included in all roads open to public use (Temel, 2019).

Today, the most common mode of transportation is road transportation. Those who prefer road traffic are both directly affected and responsible for the safety of this area. Article 7 of the Vienna Convention on Road Traffic of 1968 requires road users to refrain from any behavior that may endanger traffic or damage public or private property. However, road safety remains a global problem and no country has developed a satisfactory solution to it. scientifically, to develop safe road traffic systems. proven, long term approaches accident your reasons detection with collision It depends on the destruction of areas or making these

areas controllable by road traffic users (Şare, 2016).

According to the 2019 data of the Turkish Statistical Institute, 0.5% of the fatal and injury traffic accidents that occurred in Turkey in 2019 are due to the condition of the roads (TUIK, 2020).

ii. Vehicle

The concept of vehicle is the general name of motorized, non-motorized and special-purpose vehicles, construction machinery and rubber-wheeled tractors used on the highway (Temel, 2019). (“Highway Traffic Regulations » TR Regulations”) A low proportion of traffic accidents, compared to other elements of traffic safety, is caused by the vehicle element, but the importance of human life and the preventability of vehicle errors have made vehicles an essential element in traffic safety. The type, age, maintenance, and settings of the vehicle traveling in traffic also affect traffic safety, the weight of the accident that may occur, and thus the rate of loss of life and property. In addition, damage, and wear on some parts of the vehicles pose a risk in terms of traffic safety. Even if some of these damages and abrasions do not directly cause the accident, also win the severity, and negative results can increase, some in the evenings damage and abrasions if to accident direct cause can give. Other from the side vehicle status It also directly affects the driving conditions of the driver (Yiğitel, 2019). According to the 2019 data of the Turkish Statistical Institute, 2% of the fatal and injury traffic accidents that occurred in Turkey in 2019 are caused by vehicles (TUIK, 2020).

iii. Human

The most essential element of traffic safety is the human element. The biggest share of traffic safety violations or traffic accidents belongs to the human factor. According to the 2019 data of the Turkish Statistical Institute, the fault rate in fatal and injury traffic accidents that occurred in Turkey in 2019 belongs to the driver with 88% and pedestrians with 8.2% (TUIK, 2020). This shows that 96.2% of traffic accidents are caused by the human factor.

Within the scope of traffic safety, human element, vehicle driver, passenger, pedestrian, and

regulatory-supervisory officers (traffic police-gendarme and trainers) are included. In a study investigating the factors related to traffic accidents, it was determined that the factors causing the accidents were determined. at the beginning driver your education lack of is understood. Different much lots research too this supports. This your research in the results encountered partner a feature also traffic rules knowing and what you know conscious a way practicing of drivers traffic to accident it is less confused (Yiğitel, 2019); to accident cause giving driver behaviours to three separable. These behaviors; *on purpose and willfully breaking the rules, carelessness and carelessness, mistake, and inadequacy* . Knowingly and willingly breaking the rules is a deviation from the behavior required for safety in a potentially risky traffic environment. Offenses such as drunk driving, speeding this sample aspect can be given. Neglect if false a behaviour because of in person situations that cause discomfort. Removing the seat belt, which is thought to be too tight, is a behavior of negligence, but the person who removes the seat belt still feels uncomfortable (Yiğitel, 2019).

All the traffic accidents are caused by the interaction of the human element with the vehicle and road features. In the realization of the accident, the human element mostly plays the leading role as an active and passive element in this interaction. Human perception ability, sense of responsibility, age, fatigue, psychological states such as anger or stress, vision and hearing capacity, attention, reaction speed, reasoning ability, habits, education, and experience as many lots of accidents caused by human factor affects. Moreover, infrastructure services and engineering studies with vehicle of their condition end It is not enough to prevent human errors. These measures will only lead to a small reduction in the rate of accidents. The main thing is to improve the human element as the most essential element (Çelik, 2007).

2. Indirectly Affecting Traffic Safety Elements

"Traffic the safety of indirect affecting elements; education, audit and accident post- from assistance services consists of."

a. Education

The concept of education is the phenomenon of developing positive behaviors in people through various methods and materials. In terms of traffic safety, the behavior of vehicle users is determined by their experience and the training they have received. On the other hand, traffic education includes not only road users, drivers, passengers, and pedestrians, but also children of educational age and their educators, official units responsible for traffic control, academics, engineers who design and build roads and infrastructures, politicians, and society wide cuts of concerns. Therefore, human focused and sustainable a traffic education can be considered as the most effective tool to ensure traffic safety in an ideal sense (Working Group Report, 2018).

b. Audit

The purpose of traffic control is to ensure full compliance with the traffic rules and regulations on the roads, based on the principles of learning theory and psychological deterrence. The conceptual infrastructure of traffic control is based on the deterrence principle in criminology and the learning principle in psychology. The principle of deterrence is the use of punishment to deter illegal attitudes and behaviors. and from punishment to avoid under the influence is relevant. Check, both traffic to the rules violation against your behavior to prevent both also this rules breach to try those who intend It includes deterring, imposing sanctions on violators, that is, punishing them. Therefore, for an effective control, psychological factors such as deterrence and strengthening the perception of the possibility of being caught must be considered (Sümer and Kaygısız, 2008). 2015).

In our country, traffic safety inspections have provided an increase in traffic capacity as well as a decrease in accidents, but on the other hand, there is an inadequacy of human-made inspections. With the technological developments, the efficiency of the audits has increased with the electronic environment of the audits. Nevertheless, it is necessary for drivers to feel that they are being always supervised to conduct inspections more effectively and to improve driver-human behavior (Yiğitel, 2019).

The common issues of traffic inspections conducted around the world are listed as follows;

- i. *Inspections should be intense: The public should be informed about the inspections to be conducted, and inspections should be conducted in places and times that the public does not expect, to increase the interest in the inspections.*
- ii. *The objectives of the audit should be determined well and clearly, while determining the target, the elements that are violated the most and cause the most damage are considered. should be taken.*
- iii. *Social support should be provided in the inspections, it is necessary that the inspections are made for the safety of the people. should be adopted.*
- iv. *Audits are conducted lawfully and fairly. should be conducted.*
- v. *In the audits, there should not be a shortage of personnel and sufficient personnel should be assigned. The fact that inspection personnel can be seen with their official uniforms and official vehicles is also effective in preventing accidents. is happening.*
- vi. *Punishment should not be delayed, and sanctions should be applied immediately after the violation.*
- vii. *Supervision of the audit should also be done, and innovative approaches should be developed by evaluating the results. should be determined.*
- viii. *Technology should be used in audits (Parliament, 2000).*

c. Post-Accident Assistance Services

Most of the deaths in traffic accidents occur between the first 5 minutes and the first half hour. For this reason, post-accident assistance services are of immense importance in reducing the negative consequences of traffic safety. Emergency aid provided at the scene of the accident also reduces the treatment costs and hospitalization and treatment times required by the victims. This brings a significant economic gain.

The basic principle in emergency and rescue services, rescue and first aid at the accident site measures while taking same in time of the wounded priority to the state by to where, how to move is planning. As a result, for the injured to survive after the accident; emergency call for help, first aid, rescue, emergency medical assistance, appropriate transport and hospital treatment are required (TBMM, 2020).

d. Risk Groups and Risk in Traffic Accidents factors

The groups at risk for traffic accidents are divided into three groups by the World Health Organization.

- i. **Socio-economic Status:** Traffic of accidents % ninety of them low and middle income occur in countries.*
- ii. **Age:** Young people between the ages of 15-29 make up 48% of fatal traffic accidents.*
- iii. **Gender:** Happening traffic to accidents those involved approximately third the two are men (Balun and Erbay, 2017).*

Again, the main risk factors related to traffic accidents were evaluated by dividing them into five.

- i. **Speed:** Speed is vital for traffic safety and traffic one of the main causes of accidents is one.*
- ii. **Alcohol: Drinking** and driving increases both the risk of accidents and the risk of death and injury. raises.*
- iii. **Motorcycle Helmet:** The rate of death and injury because of helmet use is up to 70% may decrease.*
- iv. **Seat Belt and Child Seat:** Using the seat belt correctly, 70% of deaths and injuries caused by traffic accidents, child seat Its use causes injuries by 80%. is reducing.*
- v. **Attention Clutter:** Attention clutter, especially also in traffic cruising on the go the use of mobile phones has become one of the crucial*

factors of traffic accidents (Balun and Erbay, 2017).

3. Traffic Safety Risk perception

One of the factors affecting traffic safety behaviors is risk perception. People tend to evaluate risks differently in different situations. The concept of risk perception can be defined as the perception of the probability of an event occurring. Other than the side risk perception, person by perceived risk level of has also been defined as Some studies have shown that traffic safety is affected by the ability to evaluate risky situations in the traffic environment. In the same studies, it was also revealed that drivers who are not good at noticing or perceiving risks in the traffic environment have more traffic accidents than drivers who are good at perceiving or noticing risks in traffic (Ersöz et al . 2019).

When this situation is evaluated in terms of our country, it would be appropriate to look at a few studies. In a study conducted to determine the perceptions of Gazi Vocational School students about risky situations in traffic, 93% of the students stated that high speed traffic security in terms of a risk aspect they evaluated however check is not It has been understood that the rate of students who think that the legal speed limit can be exceeded is 25%. Furthermore, 82% of the students thought that high speed would be dangerous even if the driver were experienced, % eighty-nine of them your speed the more vehicle of control will get stronger he knows, % ninety-five of them However, it was observed that as the speed increased, the probability of the accident resulting in death would increase very much. However, it was also stated that 46% of the same student group considered driving at high speed as a skill, 45% believed that going fast saves time, and 57% thought that they could stop in a noticeably short distance with high-tech vehicles. On the other hand, the rate of those who think that there is no need to wear a seat belt if there is an airbag in the vehicle is 65% (Öztürk et al., 2014).

In addition, it has been evaluated in terms of risk factors in a study on the statistical analysis of the effect of driver personality structure on the probability of having an accident in traffic (woman of drivers; male to drivers by vehicle in using more). They are careful and devoted, give more importance to traffic safety, the rate of accident decreases as the level of education

increases, the group with the highest rate of being involved in an accident in terms of age group is drivers between the ages of 18-25, those who use cigarettes or mobile phones while driving have more accidents than those who do not. It is understood that they do (Hasanhanoglu, 2008).

Another study was conducted to determine the stage of risky behaviors in traffic in Turkish society and to define the steps of the participants at this stage. In the study, high speed, alcohol, not using seat belts, using mobile phones and eating while driving was chosen as risky driver behaviors and the behaviors were examined based on the transtheoretical model. The transtheoretical model was used to examine behavioral changes related to traffic safety. In this model, change takes place in five steps. These steps are; the steps of pre-thinking, thinking, preparing, acting, and maintaining about change. In the findings obtained because of the research; it has been stated that most of the non-driver group are at the stage of acting about driving at speed limits and using mobile phones while driving at the maintenance stage for driving while drunk and wearing a seat belt, and at the preparation stage for eating while driving. Trustworthy drive education received the one which of drivers located to the steps. When looked at, it was seen that most of this group was in the act of acting in all risky behaviors, trustworthy drive education did not receive of drivers most of them in speed borders. It has been observed that they are at the preparatory stage for using a mobile phone while driving, and at the stage of acting while driving while drinking, using a seat belt, and eating while driving (Kaçan et al., 2018).

When the examples given, and the results of other studies are evaluated together; it is difficult to say that there is a sufficient level of knowledge and awareness about risk and risk perception in our country. It can be said that surveys and studies to be conducted with the participation of people with sufficient or elevated level of education on this subject will not be sufficient to determine the adequacy of the level of risk perception in our country. Namely; *“The level of risk perception in our country in this regard can only be revealed with extremely broad participation studies that can be done with different age and education groups in different geographical regions, considering the driver's license classes, education levels and socio-cultural levels. Decisions taken in traffic safety policies, where the level of risk perception is not determined and considered, will not be sufficient to ensure traffic safety*

in this context.

4. The Obligation of Traffic Education to School Students and Respect in Traffic

In the National Transport Strategy of the countries, improving the behavior of drivers through education, training, appropriate driver's license, and practice is considered as a core of increasing traffic and transport safety. Based on these issues, which are implemented in many countries and are present in the curricula, it is also recognized as an urgent matter to implement and strengthen targeted activities as well as institutional frameworks and capacities in the fields of implementation, engineering, education, and emergency response at the national level. However, unfortunately, it is difficult to find any well-organized traffic safety training program or material for future drivers (Lee, 1986; Al-Mansour and Al-Fozan, 1998).

Although many awareness and information meetings, trainings and seminars are held, it is seen that many elements, including respect in traffic, do not exist in the main modules of education and in the curriculum (United Nations [UN], 2016). Despite such a global trend of interest in traffic safety and the interest of current governments, it is imperative to develop an educational traffic safety curriculum consisting of important topics on traffic safety for children who will be the heroes of the future society. For these curricula, various visual tools such as cartoons, graphics and pictures can be used to help children understand better. At the regional level, the cartoon named "Tim Gendarmerie" in Turkey can be shown as the best visual example.

5. Traffic Education Starting from Primary Education

The curriculum suitable for primary school, particularly for grades 4 to 6 or equivalent age, can be summarized in four components, in line with research and practice activities:

- 1) review of international traffic safety education programs targeting primary school students or other similar age groups;*
- 2) definition of user needs for new material equipment;*

- 3) *development of target-specific material and application of visual aids to it; and*
- 4) *completion of a curriculum, including the topic “respect in traffic,” by evaluating new material. For this purpose, specific information regarding status quo data in traffic safety education and training may be collected from selected countries such as the USA, UK, Germany, Sweden, Korea, and Japan.*

Because the results obtained when the accident statistics are compared with the selected countries that provide traffic safety education in primary schools show that such an education, equipment and curriculum will be easier by getting information from the countries that are advanced in this regard. This comparison highlights the need for some early intervention in the form of educational material to improve driving behavior.

6. The Importance of the Subject in the Light of the Data

According to statistics from the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2017), an average of 235.8 traffic accidents per 100,000 people occurred in 2014, and the OECD average death rate was 7.3 per 100,000 people. The WHO reported in 2015 that “about 1.25 million people”’s lives are shortened each year because of a traffic accident (WHO, 2015b). Between 20 and 50 million more people suffer non-fatal injuries, and many become disabled because of their injuries. (“Health in Nigeria - Health in Nigeria - abcdef. wiki”) According to reports and newspapers, there were 1667.7 traffic accidents per 100,000 people, which is about seven times higher than the country average selected in this study (2016), which is one of the OECD countries. approximately 3.8 times higher than the average rate.

According to the information above, the topics in the traffic safety education material should be designed in such a way that primary school students can easily learn from their experiences in daily life. Additionally, students can correct their mistakes themselves through learning. The Curriculum Material may consist of eleven (11) sections:

1. *Safety for passengers;*
2. *Driving on highways and traffic signs;*

3. *Danger of driving in a drowsy state;*
4. *Safety rules for driving breaks on the road;*
5. *The dangers of using a mobile device while driving;*
6. *Respect*
7. *Speed;*
8. *Necessary interventions to traffic accidents;*
9. *Inclement weather driving;*
10. *Traffic safety in urban areas; and*
11. *Emergency vehicle purchase (KSU, 2017).*

Again, it will be important in terms of perception interpretation that students leave additional comments that they want to be reflected in the traffic safety education system. Teachers can facilitate curriculum development by integrating traffic safety education into the school curriculum and consulting with relevant authorities to subdivide the program into various primary school grades. Also, the suggestion that a part of school activities should be devoted to the topic of traffic safety can be highlighted by the teachers' comments, the need for similar material on the topic of safety in using the school bus.

There are many studies in the literature, especially on children. Their primary purpose was to assess how students perceive traffic safety and to update the topic and get an idea of the composition of our traffic safety training material. Again, there are results where the aim is to compare the new perceptions that the student received from a pilot training class on traffic safety using the new material. According to the results of the literature review, approximately 84% of the students answered positively to a question asked to assess whether they know what traffic safety and respect are; also, a significant improvement was seen in correct answer rates. After the training, an increase of approximately 24% (correct answer rate: 49% - 73%) compared to the pre-training was noted.

The figure shows the average responses of students before and after the training lesson. In addition to the selected traffic safety areas, the amount of improvement achieved due to the training course given in each of the "respect in traffic" element is available in the chart. It is noted that traffic signs and human factor topics are difficult for students to understand (Before – After the Education).

As a result,

- 1) raising children with special interests and
- 2) There is a need to prepare complementary courses on these subjects.¹

7. Traffic Culture, Respect for Traffic Rules, and Individuals

Culture is defined as “the sum of all the material and spiritual values created in the historical and social development process and the tools used in creating and transmitting them to the next generations, showing the extent of man's dominance over his natural and social environment...” (tdk.gov.tr, 2010b). It also means the knowledge gained by the individual in the environment in which he lives. In a broad sense, culture encompasses all human thoughts and behaviors. Including safety, beliefs, behavior patterns, habits, values, rules, that is, everything that people guide in their daily activities creates their culture (“Traffic Safety Culture in Turkey | GEZENBİLİR FORUM”).

¹Developing a new traffic safety training material for the future drivers in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, Seongkwan Mark Leea, Abdullah I.Al-Mansoura

As political culture, business culture, etc., is used for beliefs and customs such as restrictions, regulations, and supervision related to the term in which it is used. Traffic culture is an overly broad concept that covers all practices in traffic, including our behavior and habits in traffic. Traffic is a culture of using and sharing common space. To develop this culture, a certain period of training is required. For the individual living in the society to be willing to obey the rules, he must believe in the established order and the rules that must be followed to ensure that order, that is, he must have a grasp of the traffic culture and consciousness. It is obvious that social awareness is necessary for the formation of a traffic culture and for the permanent solution of the traffic problem (Pampal et al., 1999:30), and creating and placing the traffic culture in people through education is the only way to solve the traffic problem.

It is an indisputable fact that education has a prominent place in the development of traffic culture in individuals living in society. According to Pampal et al., (1999), the basis of traffic safety problem in Turkey is misunderstanding and perception in behaviors and attitudes towards traffic culture. Insufficient information on traffic rules and mistakes that are known to be true about traffic safety and rules are a big problem. In this context, ensuring the formation of a desired traffic culture in the society through education in formal and non-formal education institutions will make a significant contribution to eliminating the problems experienced in traffic. Because raising individuals who are conscious of traffic safety, know their responsibilities towards themselves and their environment, and have a traffic culture is only possible through education (Court of Accounts Traffic Report, 2008:38).

Tanrikulu (2003) states that no matter how modern and contemporary traffic education is offered in the education system, if a "traffic culture" is not formed or cannot be created, Turkey's traffic problem cannot be solved. The most effective way to create a desired culture in societies is through education. In other words, the training of drivers and pedestrians with the desired traffic culture can only be realized through education. Therefore, we must develop training programs that will contribute to the formation of the desired traffic culture with a planned and continuous training in our educational institutions and to raise social awareness about traffic. Tanrikulu (2003:55) states that "Traffic Safety" courses and subjects in primary and secondary education programs should be rearranged as they are practiced in contemporary countries so that traffic culture can be created in people's consciousness and subconscious, and

that "the 'known', 'done' instead of a rote education system It emphasizes that a "Traffic Culture" can be created in individuals by transforming them into.

People learn road safety principles in driving schools. But many things taught in these schools are not put into practice on the road. Courses are available based on the reality of the situation drivers face every day. Since people do not follow the traffic rules while driving, many surprises on the road require psychological alertness. While the traffic department tries to enforce rules and deal with violations, the lack of an educational approach and the general failure of drivers to comply with traffic laws cannot be ignored, of course. The biggest reason drivers who violate the law, harm people and cause chaos on the road are encountered every day is the absence of the "respect for the individual" element in the school curriculum in the education system.²

For pedestrians and drivers to act more safely alongside traffic officers, the "respect" element must be implemented and fulfilled. Many countries have solved their traffic problems by applying exactly this issue. Although this subject should be evaluated together with traffic psychology, educational psychology and child psychology, the fact that children comply with traffic rules reminds us of the curriculum deficiencies at the advanced age level and the negativities in practice knowledge and skills.

8. Conclusion and Recommendations

According to the latest data, 14.9 people die every day in Turkey due to traffic accidents, and 775.9 people are injured. In addition to this vital balance sheet, direct and indirect financial losses due to traffic accidents are too great to ignore. Despite the state and government-supported strategies and policies developed on the subject, the studies of educational institutions on the subject, and the activities of non-governmental organizations, our country still has not reached the desired level in traffic accidents. Considering that the most crucial factor in the formation of traffic accidents is the human factor, the source of the problem is understood more clearly. At this point, inadequacies in educational practices and ineffective or

² Traffic Safety Training in the European Union and Turkey Mehmet Murat Payam

ineffective legal sanctions can be cited as the two most important reasons for the inadequacy of state-based or supported policies and civil society activities related to traffic safety. Traffic education is an issue that requires careful attention and a lot of effort before and after the implementation for the curriculum. Teacher satisfaction should be recognized as the main catalyst for the success of the traffic safety program. The element of respect must of course be integrated into the curriculum as comprehensively as any other subject. To further reinforce this finding, future studies that consider larger sample size and individual perception of the school should be recommended. It should be suggested that further work be done in the context of “individual respect in traffic” to include other elements, including pedestrian behavior, drifting behavior, and school bus safety issues. It can also be expected that a series of "individual respect" traffic safety educational materials will be developed for adolescents, adults, and professionals to improve traffic safety.

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